

Perceived Supervision Scale (PSS) – Krio Version (Sierra Leone)

Fɔr tell wi bɔt u boss, duya sho aw yu gri ɔr nɔr gri wit den tɔk yah. **Duya ansa ol de kewstiyon dem. Tik de kɔrrekt ansa. nor leff enitin biyen.**

	Nɔr Gii tranga wan	A nɔr gri	Nɔr ebul disayd	Gii	A gii Tranga wan
	1	2	3	4	5
1. Mi boss dey get mitin wit mi ɔltem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2. Mi boss kin tel mi tenki	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3. Mi boss dey oltem mit wit mi for tok bot problem dem en aw wi for solv dem	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4. Mi boss dey lisin to wetin a dey tell am	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
5. Mi boss sabi make in point	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
6. Mi boss kin ep mi leh a lan mor	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>